

Oracle Configuration Discrepancies Check

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

The project is aimed to detect discrepancies between running setup and metadata repositories storing elements of configuration. The system needs to detect differences between OEM information, run-time information and configuration management data which is stored in Syscontrol LDAP.

The discrepancies might lead to service instability or unexpected behavior of the environment. Maintenance or monitoring scripts could potentially be affected as well. This is why it's crucial to detect such misconfigurations in an efficient manner.

ABSTRACT

This project is part of the 2024 CERN OpenLab Summer Student program, conducted over a 9-week internship. It aims to address the challenges of managing complex database setups within the ORACLE service at CERN, which involve clusters and multiple nodes. The primary objective is to develop a solution that continuously identifies discrepancies between the live databases configuration and external configuration sources.

Using an existing automation solution (Rundeck tool), the project implements a system to integrate data from various sources, ensuring that runtime settings are consistently aligned with stored parameters. A key aspect of the project involves detecting mismatches, such as incorrect Oracle Home paths, which could lead to potential system instabilities or failures.

The project focuses on automating the identification of configuration discrepancies and enhancing the reliability of database operations at CERN to improve the overall stability and performance of the Oracle database systems.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The ORACLE service at CERN is essential for supporting the CERN community by providing over 100 databases, most of which are RAC (Real Application Clusters) databases. This setup involves a complex infrastructure with clusters and multiple nodes within each cluster. Ensuring the reliability and consistency of these databases is crucial for the effective operation of CERN's scientific research.

In such a dynamic environment, the Oracle databases run from specific paths, involving the CRS (Cluster Ready Services) and Oracle home directories. These directories contain the necessary binaries and libraries for the database's operation. As updates and environmental changes occur within clusters and databases, it is essential to ensure that all configurations remain synchronized across various nodes and clusters. Any discrepancies in these configurations can lead to performance issues, system inefficiencies, or even failures, seriously impacting CERN's operations. Failed or manual updates can lead to synchronization issues between running configuration and metadata repositories, resulting in errors. Additionally, some repositories may incorrectly report databases as unavailable while they are available.

This project, conducted as part of the 2024 CERN OpenLab Summer Student program, seeks to address these challenges by developing a solution that continuously identifies discrepancies between live database configurations and external configuration sources. By integrating data from multiple systems, the project aims to ensure that runtime settings consistently align with stored parameters. This synchronization is necessary for maintaining the integrity, performance, and stability of the Oracle database systems at CERN.

Using a tool like Rundeck, this project automates the detection of mismatches, such as incorrect Oracle home paths and ensures that any changes in the environment are accurately reflected across all places where the configuration is stored. This approach not only reduces potential issues but also enhances the overall efficiency of database management processes at CERN. After collecting the data, a report has to be prepared and made available to the Database team.

2. DATA SOURCES

In the context of managing Oracle databases at CERN, it is necessary to understand the roles of Syscontrol LDAP [1] (Lightweight Directory Access Protocol), Running Configuration (RC), and OEM (Oracle Enterprise Manager). Each of these components plays a significant role in ensuring the efficient operation, monitoring, and synchronization of CERN's database infrastructure.

a. SYSCONTROL LDAP

At CERN, LDAP is utilized for storing and managing scripts used in the automation and configuration of Oracle database environment. The project called Syscontrol acts as a repository that maintains critical information about system configurations, ensuring that updates and changes are consistently applied across all database instances. Syscontrol LDAP can be efficiently used to manage and script maintenance tasks, which are essential for maintaining database security and functionality.

b. RUNNING CONFIGURATION

Running Configuration (RC) refers to the current setup and state of the Oracle databases as they operate within the CERN environment. It includes details such as the paths to Oracle Home and the versions of the binaries being used.

RC provides real-time information on the configuration of each server and database instance, highlighting what is actively running across the clusters. It is important for monitoring the performance of the databases,

ensuring that the operational settings are aligned with the expected configurations. Accurate running configurations enable rapid identification of discrepancies, allowing for timely corrective actions to prevent database disruptions.

c. OEM

OEM [2] is a management and monitoring tool designed for Oracle database environments. It provides a graphical interface to manage and supervise the entire database infrastructure.

At CERN, OEM serves as a vital repository containing detailed information about database clusters, instances, and configurations. It allows administrators to perform essential tasks such as monitoring the status of databases, detecting anomalies, and generating performance reports. OEM ensures optimal database system performance by quickly identifying and resolving issues. OEM system is also the source of alerting in case of database unavailability or other problems with the service delivered by the team.

3. TOOLS

To address the challenge of finding the misconfigurations, this project proposes a structured approach using Rundeck [3] automation tool. Rundeck can be used to manage and execute tasks across a distributed network of servers. It provides direct server connectivity, allowing administrators to efficiently automate tasks across multiple nodes. This is very important for configuration updates, executing diagnostic checks, and providing consistency in the Oracle database infrastructure at CERN. Moreover, Rundeck is already configured within the CERN team, enhancing the efficiency and reliability of database management by automating routine tasks. Rundeck will execute jobs based on Bash and Python scripts, in addition to processing SQL statements.

4. PROPOSED SOLUTION

The solution involves creating several jobs in Rundeck. A main Rundeck job will launch multiple smaller jobs called helpers. Each helper job will collect data from different repositories and store it into a dedicated table in an Oracle schema created for this project. This setup ensures that all relevant data is aggregated, and discrepancies are identified efficiently.

a. COLLECTING SYSCONTROL LDAP DATA

The first step in the proposal involves implementing a job helper that collects data from the Syscontrol LDAP repository using the *vegas-cli* command. This command is developed internally and is the main way of accessing the information stored in Syscontrol LDAP. The Rundeck helper job gathers essential configuration details of each database entity. The job is collecting information about versions and Oracle Home paths, related to Oracle database setup.

Once the data is collected, it is processed to ensure that it is relevant and accurate before being stored in the project's Oracle database. This process allows for the effective monitoring and comparison of live configurations against the stored parameters.

In addition to discrepancies in the information between different repositories, some mismatches can be found between the `SC_VERSION` parameter and the `SC_ORACLE_HOME` parameter. This is an example of some discrepancies found in LDAP:

LDAP_SUBCATEG...	LDAP_ENTITY	LDAP_VERSION	LDAP_HOME_PATH
CMAN	CMAN_ATLAS01_PROD	12.1.0.1.0	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/cman1940
CMAN	CMAN_GEN01_PROD	12.1.0.1.0	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/cman
RAC	POSTM_TN02_RAC54	rdbms19170_cern2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1921_cern2
RAC	CSDBC1_CLONE	rdbms19123_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1923_cern1
RAC	INT2R_INTDBS_RAC16	rdbms1921_cern0	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1921_cern
RAC	ATLR_ATLR_RAC54	rdbms1921_cern2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms19121_cern2
CRS	INTDBS_RAC17	oracle-crs-crs1923_cern1.x86_64	/CRS/dbs01/crs1923_cern1
CRS	TESTDBS_RAC17	oracle-crs-crs1923_cern1.x86_64	/CRS/dbs01/crs1923_cern1
CRS	ACC_RAC17	oracle-crs-crs1923_cern1.x86_64	/CRS/dbs01/crs1923_cern1
CRS	DEVDBS1_RAC17	oracle-crs-crs1923_cern1.x86_64	/CRS/dbs01/crs1923_cern1

Figure 1. Table of LDAP discrepancies

In a normal situation, the LDAP_VERSION should contain the last part of the path mentioned in the LDAP_HOME_PATH column. However, due to some manual operations, sometimes the LDAP_VERSION column contains values different than expected. This could be caused by some script failed runs or potential typos while doing manual interventions by the database team.

As the next step, the helper job connects to a dedicated Oracle database schema *discrepancies_project* and inserts discrepancies and clean data into two different tables, ensuring that the information reflects the latest LDAP configuration status. This is an example overview of some LDAP rows of data:

LDAP_NAME	LDAP_HOME_PATH
ACCCON_ACC_RAC16	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1921_cern2
ACCCONC1_CLONE	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1921_cern2
ACCCONC2_CLONE	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms19170_cern2
ACCCONC3_CLONE	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1921_cern2
ACCCONC4_CLONE	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1921_cern2
ACCCON_GEN03_NRAC	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1921_cern2
ACCCON_TN01_RAC54	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1921_cern2
ACCCON5_CLONE	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1921_cern2
ACCINT_INTDBS_RAC16	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1921_cern2
ACC_RAC16	/CRS/dbs01/crs19180_cern1
ACCTST_TESTDBS_RAC16	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1921_cern2
ADCR_ADCRNEW_RAC52	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1921_cern2
ADCR_ADCRNEW_RAC54	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1921_cern2
ADCRNEW_RAC52	/CRS/dbs01/crs1921
ADCRNEW_RAC54	/CRS/dbs01/crs1921_cern1
AIMILIOS_ATEST_RAC54	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1923_cern1

Figure 2. Table of LDAP data.

b. COLLECTING RUNNING CONFIGURATION DATA

The second job helper focuses on gathering Running Configuration (RC) data, which involves connecting to all servers within the database environment. The job is designed to execute a script on each available server to collect essential configuration details, such as cluster names, database unique names, instance names, and Oracle Home paths.

Once connected to the servers, the script is executed on these nodes, and it extracts key information about the databases and their configurations. This includes details from the *olr.loc* configuration file, where the information about installed Oracle Clusterware is stored. The script also extracts other information about

the Oracle Clusterware environment, e.g. the cluster name. The collected data is then sent back to the main rundock job, where it is processed to ensure accuracy and relevance.

A discrepancy in the Running Configuration is identified when there is a mismatch between the Clusterware location used by different database nodes in the cluster. This situation is theoretically possible (and accepted) during the clusterware patching/upgrade process. However, it's not an accepted situation outside of the short period of the patching process. To simplify, if the Clusterware ORACLE_HOME path indicates a different location in two nodes of the same cluster, it is marked as a discrepancy. Another type of discrepancy happens when no database instances are running on a server, which could mean a potential infrastructure problem. These discrepancies are shown as rows containing the database name and its home path, but with multiple rows for each expected instance, where the data from the servers is null. This is an example of some discrepancies found in RC:

RC_DB_UNIQUE_NAME	RC_DB_HOME_PATH	RC_DB_INSTANCE_NAME	RC_DB_INSTANCE_HOME_PATH
ACCCONC2_CLONE	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2	(null)	(null)
ACCCONC2_CLONE	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2	(null)	(null)
ACCCONC1_CLONE	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2	(null)	(null)
ACCCONC1_CLONE	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2	(null)	(null)
ACCCON5_CLONE	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2	(null)	(null)
ACCCON5_CLONE	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2	(null)	(null)
ACCCONC4_CLONE	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2	(null)	(null)
ACCCONC4_CLONE	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2	(null)	(null)
ACCCON_ACC_RAC17	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2	(null)	(null)
ACCCON_ACC_RAC17	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2	(null)	(null)
ACCCONC3_CLONE	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2	(null)	(null)
ACCCONC3_CLONE	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2	(null)	(null)

Figure 3. Table of RC discrepancies.

The script also connects to a dedicated Oracle database schema *discrepancies_project* and inserts discrepancies and clean data into two different tables, ensuring that the information reflects the latest RC configuration status. This is an overview of RC rows of data:

RC_NAME	RC_HOME_PATH
INFORLND_AISTEST_RAC16	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms18110_jvml8110_cern1
INFORLND_AISTEST_RAC16_INFORLND1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms18110_jvml8110_cern1
INFORLND_AISTEST_RAC16_INFORLND2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms18110_jvml8110_cern1
INFORLNT_AISTEST_RAC16	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1
INFORLNT_AISTEST_RAC16_INFORLNT1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1
INFORLNT_AISTEST_RAC16_INFORLNT2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1
INFRA_RAC54	/CRS/dbs01/crs1923_cern1
INTDBS_RAC16	/CRS/dbs01/crs1923_cern1
INTDB11_INTDBS_RAC16	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern0
INTDB11_INTDBS_RAC16_INTDB111	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern0
INTDB11_INTDBS_RAC16_INTDB112	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern0
INTDB19_DEVDBS1_RAC17	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1
INTDB19_DEVDBS1_RAC17_INTDB191	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1
INTDB19_DEVDBS1_RAC17_INTDB192	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1
INT12R_INTDBS_RAC16	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern0

Figure 4. Table of RC data.

c. COLLECTING OEM DATA

The third job helper focuses on gathering data from Oracle Enterprise Manager (OEM), a tool for managing and monitoring Oracle databases. This job is designed to collect configuration details from OEM and identify discrepancies between the reported settings and the actual runtime configurations. A key part of this process involves creating and using a database link to access data stored in the OEM repository.

A database link is a schema object that allows queries to be executed on a remote database as if they were running locally. The following SQL command creates the database link using the credentials of a read-only user:

```
CREATE DATABASE LINK oem_db CONNECT TO sysman_ro IDENTIFIED BY "password" USING
'@oem_service_prod';
```

Once the database link is established, it can be used to query tables in the OEM database. To differentiate data accessed through the link, the table names in the query are appended with '@oem_db'. This job helper retrieves target names, types, and Oracle Home paths for various database environments, including Oracle databases, RAC clusters, and standalone instances.

The job helper processes the data to detect discrepancies, particularly by comparing the rac_database and oracle_database entries. If there is a mismatch between the Oracle Home paths for a RAC database and its corresponding instances, it is marked as a discrepancy. These discrepancies are shown as rows containing the database name and its home path, but with multiple rows for each instance, each with a different home path. Such discrepancies can be fixed by re-applying the OEM target Oracle Home path configuration or running a dedicated Rundeck job. At the moment of writing this report, it was unclear what created that type of discrepancies in internal OEM repository. An example of some discrepancies found in OEM is shown below:

OEM_DB_UNIQUE_NAME	OEM_DB_HOME_PATH	OEM_DB_INSTANCE_NAME	OEM_DB_INSTANCE_HOME_PATH
AISBIP_AIS2_RAC55	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms19170_cern1	AISBIP_AIS2_RAC55_AISBIP1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1923_cern1
AISBIP_AIS2_RAC55	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms19170_cern1	AISBIP_AIS2_RAC55_AISBIP2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1923_cern1
AISBIP_DEVDBS2_RAC17	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1921_cern2	AISBIP_DEVDBS2_RAC17_AISBIP2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1923_cern1
AISBIP_DEVDBS2_RAC17	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1921_cern2	AISBIP_DEVDBS2_RAC17_AISBIP1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1923_cern1
AISDBP_AIS_NRAC	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms19170_cern1	AISDBP_AIS_NRAC_AISDBP2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1923_cern1
AISDBP_AIS_NRAC	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms19170_cern1	AISDBP_AIS_NRAC_AISDBP1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1923_cern1
AISDBP_DEVDBS2_RAC17	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1921_cern2	AISDBP_DEVDBS2_RAC17_AISDBP2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1923_cern1
AISDBP_DEVDBS2_RAC17	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1921_cern2	AISDBP_DEVDBS2_RAC17_AISDBP1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1923_cern1
AISDBS_AISTEST_RAC16	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1921_cern2	AISDBS_AISTEST_RAC16_AISDBS2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1923_cern1
AISDBS_AISTEST_RAC16	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1921_cern2	AISDBS_AISTEST_RAC16_AISDBS1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbms1923_cern1

Figure 5. Table of OEM discrepancies.

The script also connects to a dedicated Oracle database schema *discrepancies_project* and inserts discrepancies and clean data into two different tables, ensuring that the information reflects the latest OEM configuration status. This is an overview of OEM rows of data:

OEM_NAME	OEM_HOME_PATH
AIS2_RAC55	/CRS/dbs01/crs1921_cern1
AIS3_RAC55	/CRS/dbs01/crs1921_cern1
ALIONR_ALIONR_DCSRAC	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2
ALIONR_ALIONR_DCSRAC_ALIONR1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2
ALIONR_ALIONR_DCSRAC_ALIONR2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2
ALIONR_DCSRAC	/CRS/dbs01/crs1921_cern1
ALIONR_PHY3_RAC54	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2
ALIONR_PHY3_RAC54_ALIONR1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2
ALIONR_PHY3_RAC54_ALIONR2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2
ATLARC_MISC_RAC54	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms19170_cern1
ATLARC_MISC_RAC54_ATLARC1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms19170_cern1
ATLARC_MISC_RAC54_ATLARC2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms19170_cern1
ATL_NRAC	/CRS/dbs01/crs1923_cern1
ATLR_ATL_NRAC	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern3
ATLR_ATL_NRAC_ATLR1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern3
ATLR_ATL_NRAC_ATLR2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern3
ATLR_ATLR_RAC54	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2
ATLR_ATLR_RAC54_ATLR1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2
ATLR_ATLR_RAC54_ATLR2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2

Figure 6. Table of OEM data.

5. DISCREPANCIES OUTPUT

After inserting all the data and identifying internal discrepancies within each data source, the next step is to detect discrepancies between LDAP, RC, and OEM data. These cross-system discrepancies provide a view of configuration mismatches across different repositories and runtime configuration when there are mismatches or missing values for the same cluster or database including instances. The attached image provides examples of how these discrepancies appear in the output, allowing for a clearer understanding of the issues that need to be resolved.

NAME	LDAP_HOME_PATH	RC_HOME_PATH	OEM_HOME_PATH
ACCCON_ACC_RAC17	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2	(null)
ACCCONC2_CLONE	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2	(null)
ACC_RAC17	/CRS/dbs01/crs1923_cern1	/CRS/dbs01/crs1923_cern1	(null)
AIMILIOS_INFRA_RAC54	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	(null)
AIMILIOS_INFRA_RAC54_AIMILIOS1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	(null)
AIMILIOS_INFRA_RAC54_AIMILIOS2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	(null)
AISDBS_AISTEST_RAC16	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2
BAAN6D_AISTEST_RAC16	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2
BAAN6T_AISTEST_RAC16	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2
CSDB_TESTDBS_RAC16	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms19170_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1
CSDB_TESTDBS_RAC16_CSDB1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms19170_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1
CSDB_TESTDBS_RAC16_CSDB2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms19170_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1
INFORLNT_AISTEST_RAC16	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2
INT2R_INTDBS_RAC16	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern0	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern0
INT2R_INTDBS_RAC16_INT2R1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern0	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern0
INT2R_INTDBS_RAC16_INT2R2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern0	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern0
PAYD_AISTEST_RAC16	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2
PAYR_AISTEST_RAC16	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2
PAYT_AISTEST_RAC16	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1921_cern2
TDE_PDB_NRAC	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/rdbsms1923_cern1	(null)

Figure 7. Table of cross-system discrepancies.

6. DISCREPANCIES RESOLUTION

An HTML view was developed to centralize the management of these discrepancies. This view categorizes discrepancies into LDAP, RC, OEM repositories, and cross-system discrepancies, displaying each in its own table. A key feature of this view is the integration of a "Fix Discrepancy" button within the cross-system discrepancies table. This button links to a Rundeck job that updates both LDAP and OEM home paths with the correct running configuration information. The job parameters are prefilled based on the RC_HOME_PATH value. Manual verification of values is necessary before executing the corrective job.

DISCREPANCIES				
NAME	LDAP_HOME_PATH	RC_HOME_PATH	OEM_HOME_PATH	FIX DISCREPANCIES
ACCCON5_CLONE_RAC17	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1921_cem2	N/A	N/A	
ACCCONC1_CLONE_RAC17	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1921_cem2	N/A	N/A	
ACCCONC2_CLONE	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1921_cem2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1921_cem2	N/A	Solve Discrepancy
ACCCONC2_CLONE_RAC17	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1921_cem2	N/A	N/A	
ACCCONC3_CLONE_RAC17	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1921_cem2	N/A	N/A	
ACCCONC4_CLONE_RAC17	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1921_cem2	N/A	N/A	
ACCCON_ACC_RAC17	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1921_cem2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1921_cem2	N/A	Solve Discrepancy
ACC_RAC17	/CRS/dbs01/crs1923_cem1	/CRS/dbs01/crs1923_cem1	N/A	
AIMILIOS_INFRA_RAC54	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1923_cem1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1923_cem1	N/A	Solve Discrepancy
AIMILIOS_INFRA_RAC54_AIMILIOS1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1923_cem1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1923_cem1	N/A	Solve Discrepancy
AIMILIOS_INFRA_RAC54_AIMILIOS2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1923_cem1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1923_cem1	N/A	Solve Discrepancy
AISBID2_CLONE	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1921_cem2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1923_cem1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1921_cem2	Solve Discrepancy
AISBID2_CLONE_AISBID21	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1921_cem2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1923_cem1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1921_cem2	Solve Discrepancy
AISBID2_CLONE_AISBID22	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1921_cem2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1923_cem1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1921_cem2	Solve Discrepancy
AISBIT2_CLONE	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1921_cem2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1923_cem1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1921_cem2	Solve Discrepancy
AISBIT2_CLONE_AISBIT21	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1921_cem2	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1923_cem1	/ORA/dbs01/oracle/product/dbms1921_cem2	Solve Discrepancy

Figure 8. Table of cross-system discrepancies with fix button.

In addition, as a part of the project, all internal discrepancies identified within the LDAP and OEM configurations were successfully resolved. LDAP discrepancies were addressed by manually updating the SC_VERSION parameter in LDAP to match the SC_ORACLE_HOME paths. OEM discrepancies, which involved mismatches between the database home path and the instance home path, were properly resolved using the dedicated Rundeck job.

Moreover, a table was created to log data refresh times, including the timestamp when data was fetched from each repository. This ensures that the most recent information is used for the report. The execution time of the report itself is also recorded.

This report was generated on 2024/08/27 12:07:17.

DATA FETCH LOG

NAME	RUN_DATE
LDAP	2024/08/27 10:52:40
RC	2024/08/27 11:06:23
OEM	2024/08/27 11:03:32

Figure 9. Table of data fetch log.

Finally, Rundeck was configured to automatically send an email containing the HTML report to all interested team members. This ensures that everyone stays informed about the status of discrepancies and can take action as needed.

7. CONCLUSION

The developed monitoring solution has successfully detected minor configuration errors in the Oracle Database environment at CERN. Most of the errors were cleaned-up as a part of the project with some of them requiring further investigation. The proposed solution will play an important role in the maintenance of the Oracle Database Service. What is more, the corrective action job was configured to allow fixing the detected misconfigurations in an efficient way.

Through this project, Isidro has gained hands-on experience with advanced tools and technologies, including Rundeck, Oracle databases, and scripting languages such as Python and Bash. The project has allowed Isidro to deepen the understanding of the complexities involved in managing and synchronizing large-scale database infrastructures. It has also highlighted the importance of automation in maintaining system integrity and performance.

8. REFERENCES

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